

COMPARATIVE VIDEO EDITING PROGRAMS

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The main tasks of video editing are: cutting out unnecessary video fragments, gluing together separate sections of video material, creating a transition between them, adding effects and inserting captions. There are three types of video editing: linear, non-linear and hybrid.

Key words: *video editing, montage, television, video, audio, linear editing.*

Linear editing is real-time editing. Data from several sources, for example, several cameras, comes through the switch to the receiver. Next, the director of linear editing switches the signal sources and displays what he needs on the screen. Also, linear editing is used to cut scenes without violating their sequence.

With nonlinear editing, the video is converted to digital form after it is divided into fragments, then these fragments are recorded in the sequence necessary for the user, in the required format, to the selected video medium. At the same time, not all of the source video material may fall into the final file; it may be partially trimmed.

Non-linear editing came into active use on television after the advent of computers that are capable of processing digital video in real time. Such installation is carried out using special computer programs called video editors. One of the important advantages of non-linear editing is the unnecessary of completely rewriting the final video file to work with it (changing the sequence, cutting or deleting unnecessary parts of the recording).

Hybrid editing combines the advantages of linear and non-linear editing (non-linear video editing system acts as a video source). The disadvantage is usually a higher price.

Recently, non-linear editing has virtually replaced other types of video editing from our lives.

Video editing software overview

Currently, there are a fairly large number of software tools for video editing. Each of them has different functionality and is designed for users with different levels of knowledge. Consider some of the most popular video editing

software.

Рисунок 1. Adobe premiere screen.

Adobe Premiere Pro

This is just a great program with which the user can import and process a variety of video recordings, the ability to insert records of different quality and formats into one work, whether it's video from a phone or an HD-quality clip and even a movie in excess of the modern format, the program will still be able to process as you want, and at the end of the installation, transcoding is not required. A clear and accessible interface makes it easy for a novice user to work, and the number of functions provides many opportunities for a professional.

Рисунок 2. Pinnacle Studio screen.

Pinnacle Studio

With Pinnacle Studio you have the opportunity to view two imported videos in parallel and work with frames from any. The list of options includes functions such as stabilization and color correction, with which you can correct errors that occurred during recording. This is just a great program for

professional video processing, but video editing enthusiasts should consider some other video editor.

Рисунок 3. Edius Pro screen.

Edius

Professional video editor that can work with video files in 4K, 3D and HD. One of the advantages of this program is its tremendous processing and rendering speed, thanks to which the data is processed almost in real time, without any delays. Another significant advantage of this program is an unlimited number of tracks. The program is actively used to create music videos, short films and television news releases. For novice users, this program will be difficult to learn.

Рисунок 4. Movavi Video Editor screen.

Movavi Video Editor

Movavi Video Editor is a multifunctional video editor that is able to work with all popular multimedia formats. The functionality of this program has all the necessary set of tools for video processing, as well as an impressive range of effects and filters. In its simplicity, it is perfect for beginners of video editing. And in its functionality, it is not inferior to professional programs. however, the only minus of the program pushes it away from professional use - this is the number of tracks, it is one.

Рисунок 5. Sony Vegas Pro screen.

Sony Vegas Pro

SONY Vegas Pro is a representative of a family of professional video editors. It is used by television video monitors, web developers and those who produce short films. Initially, for novice users, the program interface will seem difficult to understand, but after a couple of hours of working with this program,

you will notice that all the tools are exactly where they belong.

Рисунок 6. Studio Windows (Movie Marker) screen.

Studio Windows (Movie Maker)

Everyone knows that the Windows Film Studio is a useful and time-tested video editing program. The application is perfect for beginners and is an intuitive editor for home use. This program allows you to receive video from various sources, process it using various transitions and effects, create titles, titles, cut and glue fragments. In general, the program consists of a content area, a pasteboard and a preview window. The program also has a quick access panel in which you can pin your frequently used commands. The disadvantages of the program include the fact that it has a small set of tools for working with video and saving it only in a single format — wmv. Therefore, for professionals this program is unlikely to work.

We will collect all the advantages and disadvantages of video editing software systems described above in the final table (table 1), which will clearly show us the result of the comparative analysis according to 6 criteria: number of tracks, level of effects, the ability to capture video, video resolution, paid or free access and formats are not supported by this program.

Table 1.

Comparative review of video editing software

The name of the program	Unsupported formats	Timeline tracks	Effects	Effects	Resolution	Spread
Adobe Premiere Pro	-	∞	super	+	4K	Trial
Pinnacle Studio	RM, QT	12	normal	-	1080p	Trial

Edius	-	∞	super	+	4K	Trial
Movavi Video Editor	QT, RM, FLV	1	normal	-	1080p	Trial
Sony Vegas Pro	-	∞	super	+	4K	Trial
Studio Windows (Movie Maker)	QT, RM, FLV	1	few	+	720p	Free

Video Editing Web Resources

In addition to software systems, video editing can also be done using various web resources. The most famous of them will be considered below.

**Рисунок 7. Studio Windows (Movie Marker) screen.
 Youtube editor**

YouTube Video Editor allows the user to edit video recordings from his profile directly in the browser. With its help, you can carry out tricky manipulations such as cutting, gluing transitions and text inserts. All this happens based on user uploaded video.

Рисунок 8. PopcornMaker screen.

PopcornMaker

PopcornMaker- It is an online editor with all the classic features. When you get to the service's website, you see an editing "table" where you can immediately start your work (cutting, gluing, transitions, text comments).

Рисунок 9. FileLab Video Editor screen.

FileLab Video Editor

The FileLab Video Editor, like the previous analogues, offers the user a standard set of functions. With it, you can process your video recordings by adding transitions and effects.

CONCLUSION

Video editing is the removal of unnecessary sections of the video and the reduction of the video sequence into one whole. But we do not just delete unnecessary parts, we compose the video in such a way that it looks as a whole, and the film does not lose its meaning. For this they use video editors. Currently, there are a huge number of them that are perfect for professionally processing video information, as well as for home video processing, to carry out classical manipulations with video files it's not even necessary to install any software, everything can be done online in a browser.

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